
IMPROVING ZERO-SHOT INDUSTRIAL DEFECT DETECTION EXPLOITING LMMS AS INVERSE REASONERS ^{*†}

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ABSTRACT

Industrial defect detection is a crucial task in manufacturing, associated with many critical applications. Recent approaches adopt the Zero-Shot Anomaly Detection (ZSAD) paradigm to address the task, utilizing an auxiliary training dataset to overcome the scarcity of labeled defective data in real-world applications, with the vast majority of them employing CLIP-based models. In this paper, we propose a novel method for improving the performance of a downstream CLIP-based model for ZSAD, leveraging LMMS as *inverse reasoners*. Particularly, we first prompt an LMM specialized for anomaly detection, in order to extract *counterfactual defect explanations* for the normal images of the auxiliary dataset. Subsequently, we introduce this knowledge to the CLIP-based model for ZSAD, in order to improve its defect discrimination ability. To do so, we extract the text embeddings from the LMM-generated counterfactual explanations using the text encoder of CLIP, and introduce an auxiliary objective that minimizes the cosine similarity between the CLIP’s image embeddings of normal images and their corresponding text embeddings that convey defect semantics. We apply the proposed method on a state-of-the-art model for ZSAD, considerably improving its performance. The proposed method can be extended to generic detection and classification tasks for improving the baseline performance of CLIP-based models.

Keywords industrial defect detection · LMMS · inverse reasoners · counterfactual defect explanations · CLIP

1 Introduction

Industrial defect detection falls under the broader task of anomaly detection, that aims at identifying atypical and irregular samples to the remaining objects, and locate their regions within the images [1]. Identifying anomalous samples in industrial products is a task of crucial importance in manufacturing, since it is associated with many critical applications, such as automated visual industrial inspection and quality control management [2, 3]. A major challenge in the anomaly detection task is the scarcity of labeled defective data, leading to the traditional unsupervised paradigm that aims at modeling the normal data distribution using normal samples of the target domain for tackling the task [4, 5]. However, in real-world scenarios, acquiring such data may be extremely challenging (e.g., detecting defects in a production line for new products), and thus the Zero-Shot Anomaly Detection (ZSAD) paradigm is widely used in contemporary research. ZSAD does not require the utilization of target-domain training data; instead auxiliary data are used for training, in order to remedy the challenges associated with data availability. The vast majority of recent methods pursuing this direction, following the exceptional zero-shot performance of the CLIP vision-language model [6], utilize CLIP-based models [7, 8, 9].

^{*}*Citation:* Maria Tzelepi, Nikolaos Dimitriou, Christos Gkogkos and Dimitrios Tzovaras, "Improving zero-shot industrial defect detection exploiting LMMS as inverse reasoners", Proc. of IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP 2026), Tampere, Finland, Sept.2026, accepted for publication.

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Large Language Models (LLMs) and Large Multimodal Models (LMMs) (also referred to as Multimodal LLMs), have lain at the core of ongoing research in both NLP and computer vision in recent years, accomplishing exceptional performance [10]. LMMs have also been utilized for addressing the ZSAD task, including models such as AnomalyGPT [11] and Anomaly-OV [12], which has also been utilized in this work.

In this paper, we address the industrial defect detection task, within the ZSAD paradigm, leveraging the emerging capabilities of LMMs. Specifically, we propose to exploit an LMM specialized to the ZSAD task, as *inverse reasoner*. More specifically, we prompt the LMM in order to obtain *counterfactual defect explanations* for the normal images of the auxiliary dataset, that is, we ask the model to treat the images as defective and justify this assessment. Subsequently, we use a state-of-the-art CLIP-based model for ZSAD, aiming to improve its performance by exploiting the LMM-generated knowledge. To do so, once the LMM-generated counterfactual defect explanations have been produced, we use the frozen text encoder of the utilized CLIP-based model to obtain the corresponding text embeddings. Then, during the training of the model for the defect detection task, we introduce an additional auxiliary objective that minimizes the cosine similarity between the normal image embeddings and their corresponding sample-specific text embeddings that convey defect semantics. In this way, enhanced defect discrimination ability is achieved, exploiting LMMs in a novel way, using also only normal images. In this paper, we used the AF-CLIP model, which to the best of our knowledge represents the current state-of-the-art. However, it should be emphasized that the proposed methodology is not tied to any specific architecture, contrariwise it is model-agnostic and can also be applied to other CLIP-based models for ZSAD, while it can also be extended to generic detection and classification tasks that utilize CLIP-based architectures.

The main contributions of the paper can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a novel method for improving CLIP-based models for industrial ZSAD leveraging LMMs as *Inverse Reasoners*.
- The proposed method enhances the discrimination between normal and defective embeddings, using only normal images, by exploiting the LMM-generated counterfactual defect explanations.
- The proposed method is model-agnostic, it can be applied to any CLIP-based model for ZSAD; additionally, it can be extended to generic detection and classification task for improving the baseline performance of CLIP-based models.
- The experimental evaluation on two industrial defect detection tasks, validates the effectiveness of the proposed method, improving the state-of-the-art performance.

The remainder of the manuscript is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses prior CLIP-based approaches for ZSAD. Section 3 presents in detail the proposed methodology for improving the ZSAD performance. Section 4 presents the experiments conducted in order to validate the effectiveness of the proposed method, while Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of this work.

2 Prior Work

In this section we discuss previous CLIP-based methods for ZSAD. The seminal work for addressing the industrial defect detection task within the ZSAD paradigm introduced the WinCLIP model [7]. WinCLIP, focusing on language, first proposes a prompt ensemble strategy in order to better describe normal and anomalous states. In addition, in order to address the pixel-level classification, proposes to extract and aggregate multi-scale spatial features aligned with language. Next, APRIL-GAN [13], following the same prompt design strategy, it proposes to use a linear adapter for projecting fine-grained patch features into a joint embedding space.

Subsequently, AnomalyCLIP [14] proposes to learn object-agnostic text prompts capturing generic normality and abnormality in images, in order to enhance CLIP’s understanding of the visual normality/abnormality beyond class- semantics. Furthermore, it proposes both image-level and pixel-level loss functions, in order to learn generic normality and abnormality both globally and locally. In a similar direction, AdaCLIP [15] proposes to learn so-called hybrid prompts, i.e., static prompts and dynamic prompts. The former ones are shared across all images, while the latter ones are produced for each test image. SimCLIP [16] aims to improve the misalignment between language and vision features using a multi-hierarchy vision adapter and a learnable task-specific prompt embedding. Bayes-PFL [17] models the prompt space as a learnable probability distribution, using a prompt flow module that learns both image-specific and image-agnostic distributions which are jointly used as regularizers to the text prompt space. Also, a residual cross-model attention module is designed for better aligning the dynamic text embeddings with image embeddings.

Furthermore, AA-CLIP [8] aims to embed anomaly-aware information into CLIP through a method consisting of two stages. In the first stage, the text encoder is adapted with frozen visual encoder, producing for each class the so-called anchors for anomaly-aware semantics. In the second stage, patch-level visual features are aligned with the

adapted text anchors. In both stages, simple residual adapter are introduced, keeping the original CLIP parameters frozen, in order to preserve the CLIP’s pretrained knowledge and achieve the adaptation to the task. Finally, AF-CLIP [9], which is used in this paper, also introduces a lightweight attention adapter at the output of the layers of CLIP’s visual encoder. Keeping the encoder’s parameters frozen, the adapter is finetuned, adapting CLIP to focus on local anomalies. Furthermore, a spatial aggregation step is performed before the feature adaptation by multi-scale sliding windows, while a patch alignment loss is also utilized in order to preserve the discrimination between the visual features of normal and anomalous patches. Apart from the visual adaptations, a prompt learning technique is also applied. Notably, the proposed method is orthogonal to the aforementioned CLIP-based approaches for ZSAD. It can be applied to the CLIP’s image-text embedding space for enhancing the discrimination between normal and anomalous images, exploiting LMM-generated knowledge.

3 Proposed Method

1. Extraction of counterfactual defect explanations

2. Training CLIP-based model with additional objective exploiting LMM as Inverse Reasoner

Figure 1: Proposed method: In the first stage we prompt the LMM with the normal images along with the depicted text query in order to extract counterfactual defect explanations for the normal images. In the second stage we train the downstream CLIP-based model for ZSAD (i.e., AF-CLIP) with an additional objective that minimizes the cosine similarity between each global normal image embedding and their corresponding text embedding of the LMM-generated counterfactual explanations, aiming to enhance the defect discrimination. Normal image-text embedding pairs are printed in the same color. Note that the figure illustrates only the additional proposed objective, and not the original’s AF-CLIP training objectives.

In this paper we propose to use LMMs as *inverse reasoners* for improving the ZSAD performance. To do so, as illustrated in Fig. 1, we use Anomaly-OV model to extract counterfactual knowledge for the normal images of the auxiliary dataset, and then use this knowledge to improve the performance of the AF-CLIP model. In the following, we briefly present the Anomaly-OV and AF-CLIP models, and subsequently, we present the proposed methodology.

3.1 Preliminaries

3.1.1 Anomaly-OV

Even though LMMs have demonstrated strong general visual reasoning capabilities, existing general-purpose models struggle to detect and describe subtle anomalies. To this end, Anomaly-OV is designed for ZSAD and fine-grained anomaly reasoning, by extending LLaVA-OneVision [18] with a dedicated anomaly expert, which operates on multi-level ViT features [19]. Specifically, these features are extracted from four intermediate transformer layers, processed through lightweight adapters, and fed into a look-twice feature matching (LTFM) mechanism. LTFM uses a global embedding from the original image along with learnable anomalous and normal embeddings to compute patch-level significance maps using cosine similarity and softmax weighting. Anomaly-OV is trained through a streamlined

two-phase process. First, its anomaly expert is optimized with image-level anomaly labels from the large-scale Anomaly-Instruct-125k dataset. Subsequently, the expert is frozen and the language model is instruction-tuned using a mixture of Anomaly-Instruct-125k and roughly 350k general vision-language samples from LLaVA-OneVision.

3.1.2 AF-CLIP

AF-CLIP aims to improve the CLIP’s defect detection effectiveness by introducing a lightweight adaptor module based on trainable attention mechanisms, as well as a spatial aggregation module before the adaptor. More specifically, considering the CLIP’s image encoder $f_I(\cdot)$, text encoder $f_T(\cdot)$, and projection head $f_P(\cdot)$, first the image encoder is partitioned into four hierarchical blocks, $\mathcal{L} = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, and the visual features are extracted from each block. That is, for an input image x : $a^\ell = [a_{CLS}^\ell, a_1^\ell, \dots, a_N^\ell] = f_I^\ell(x) \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times d}$, where $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, while a_{CLS}^ℓ and $\{a_i^\ell\}_{i=1}^N$ are the global and patch tokens respectively. Then, the patch features a^ℓ are reshaped into spatial feature maps b^ℓ and spatial aggregation is performed under different window sizes $r \in \mathcal{R} = 1, 3, 5$, resulting to the aggregated features $\tilde{b}^{\ell r} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$, which combined with the class token, form the multi-scale visual features: $c^{\ell r} = [a_{CLS}^\ell; \tilde{b}^{\ell r}]$. Then, the spatial-aware features $c^{\ell r}$ are fed to the adaptor $\mathcal{H}_a(\cdot)$ to obtain the anomaly-relevant visual features $\tilde{c}^{\ell r} = \mathcal{H}_a(c^{\ell r})$, which are then projected into the joint image-text space using the projection head f_P of the original CLIP: $z^{\ell r} = f_P(\tilde{c}^{\ell r}) \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times t}$, where t is the dimension of the final visual features. Regarding the text features, a prompt learning approach is developed, using fixed state-descriptive suffixes (i.e., with/without defect) and learnable parameters, i.e., \tilde{P}_a and P_n respectively. These prompts are propagated to the text encoder f_T to obtain the anomalous and normal representations, that is, $t_a = f_T(\tilde{P}_a)$ and $t_n = f_T(P_n)$. Finally, the anomaly scores are computed by aligning, using cosine similarity, the visual features and text embedding prompts. The whole score, measuring the overall similarity between the i -th visual feature and the embeddings of normal/anomalous text prompts, is computed by summing the score over all blocks ℓ and scales r , and then the probability for a visual token being anomalous is denoted as p_i , $i \in \{CLS, 1, \dots, N\}$; p_{CLS} is used for the classification loss, while p_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$ for the segmentation loss. That is, the AF-CLIP model, with frozen the pretrained CLIP, trains the parameters of the adaptor and learnable prompt embeddings, using three loss components: the image-level classification loss, $\mathcal{L}_{cls} = Focal_Loss(p_{CLS}, y)$ where y denotes the image-level class label, the pixel-level segmentation loss, $\mathcal{L}_{seg} = Focal_Loss(\tilde{P}, \tilde{M}) + L_1(\tilde{P}, \tilde{M})$, where $\tilde{P} = Reshape([p_1, \dots, p_N])$ and \tilde{M} the resized pixel-level labels, and the patch alignment loss, \mathcal{L}_{pal} which is applied on patch level features $z_i^{\ell r}$ to improve their discrimination ability.

3.2 Exploiting LMMs as Inverse Reasoners for ZSAD

The proposed methodology consists of two stages. We consider the auxiliary dataset $\{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{M}\}$ that contains normal and anomalous images, $x \in \mathcal{X}$, along with the image-level labels $y \in \mathcal{Y}$, and pixel-level labels $M \in \mathcal{M}$. In the first stage, we utilize Anomaly-OV to obtain *counterfactual defect explanations* for the normal images of the auxiliary dataset, $\{x|y = 0\}$. To do so, we prompt the LMM with the normal images along with the text query: *Consider a quality control task in manufacturing. Assume that the product shown in the image is defective. Briefly explain why it is defective and describe the specific aspects of the image that indicate the defect.*

Subsequently, in the second stage we introduce the knowledge acquired in the first stage to the training process of AF-CLIP. To do so, considering as ce^n the counterfactual defect explanation of a normal image, we first compute its text embedding. That is, given the frozen CLIP’s text encoder f_T , the text embedding is computed as: $t_{ce}^n = f_T(ce^n)$. Next, our goal is to force the global image embeddings of normal images to be less similar, in terms of cosine similarity, to their corresponding LMM-generated text embeddings that convey sample-specific defect semantics. That is, considering a global normal embedding $\{z_{CLS}^\ell | y = 0\}$; note that we use the deepest transformer layer, i.e., $\ell = 4$, since it provides the most semantically rich representation, and denote it as z_{CLS}^n for simplicity, and its corresponding text embedding of counterfactual explanation t_{ce}^n , the additional objective \mathcal{L}_{IR} , is formulated as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{IR} = \frac{z_{CLS}^n \cdot t_{ce}^n}{\|z_{CLS}^n\| \|t_{ce}^n\|}. \quad (1)$$

By minimizing eq. (1) we achieve enhanced defect discrimination ability, leveraging LMM-generated knowledge, and using only normal images. The total loss for training the AF-CLIP with the proposed additional objective, as well as the originals AF-CLIP’s training objectives is formulated as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{cls} + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{seg} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{pal} + \lambda_3 \mathcal{L}_{IR}, \quad (2)$$

where the parameters λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 control the contribution of the corresponding loss components. We should finally note that even though the proposed methodology acquires the counterfactual defect explanations for the normal images at global level, and in turn the proposed objective is applied at the global image embeddings, it could be extended

to patch level, i.e., to also minimize the cosine similarity between the patch image embeddings of normal images, $\{z_i^r, i = 1, \dots, N \mid y = 0\}$ and their corresponding text embedding. Experiments indicate that this extension can provide further improvements at pixel level.

4 Experimental Evaluation

In this section we present the experimental evaluation of the proposed method, including the description of the utilized datasets and evaluation metrics, the implementation details, as well as the evaluation results.

4.1 Datasets and Evaluation Metrics

We use two common industrial datasets to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method for ZSAD: MVTEC [20] and VISA [21]. We follow the same experimental setup as in AF-CLIP (which serves as baseline). That is, for the evaluation on MVTEC, we train our model using the test data of VISA, while we use the test data from MVTEC and evaluate the zero-shot performance on VISA. As evaluation metric we use the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC). We compute AUROC at both image and pixel levels.

4.2 Implementation Details

Following AF-CLIP, we use the frozen CLIP (ViT-L/14 @336px) model and train the learnable prompts and the additional adapters, using the same values for all the parameters. That is, image size is set to 518, the learnable embedding lengths to 12, the learning rate to 1e-4, and the batch size to 8, while the parameters λ_1 and λ_2 , as well the parameter λ_3 of the proposed auxiliary objective in eq. (2) are set to 1. The models are trained for 2 epochs. In order to ensure fairness in the comparisons, and since AF-CLIP constitutes our baseline, we reproduce the AF-CLIP experiments using the parameters reported in the original work. All the experiments are conducted using an NVIDIA RTX A4500 with 20GB of GPU memory.

4.3 Experimental Results

In Table 1 we present the evaluation results of the proposed method, denoted as AF-CLIP + IR, against AF-CLIP which serves as our baseline. We also include, for completeness, several recent CLIP-based state-of-the-art methods. Best results are printed in bold. As it demonstrated, the proposed method significantly improves the AF-CLIP’s performance, which currently represents the state-of-the-art, at image level, since it is applied at the global image embeddings. It also slightly improves the performance at pixel level on the one dataset, since the patch embeddings are indirectly optimized. As mentioned previously, the proposed objective can also be extended at the patch embeddings, so as to further improve the model’s pixel-level performance. To this aim, we also perform experiments forcing the patch embeddings of normal images to be less similar to their corresponding LMM-generated text embedding. Such extension further improves AUROC at pixel level, as it is demonstrated in Table 1.

Method	MVTEC		VISA	
	I-AUROC	P-AUROC	I-AUROC	P-AUROC
WinCLIP [7] (CVPR 2023)	91.8	85.1	78.1	79.6
APRIL-GAN [13] (CVPR-W 2023)	86.1	87.6	78.0	94.2
AnomalyCLIP [14] (ICLR 2024)	91.5	91.1	82.1	95.5
AdaCLIP [15] (ECCV 2024)	89.2	88.7	85.8	95.5
SimCLIP [16] (ACMMM 2024)	90.0	91.8	83.1	95.6
AA-CLIP [8] (CVPR 2025)	90.5	91.9	84.6	95.5
Bayes-PFL [17] (CVPR 2025)	92.3	91.8	87.0	95.6
AF-CLIP [9] (ACMMM 2025)	92.3	92.2	87.9	96.1
AF-CLIP + IR	93.2	92.2	88.6	96.2
AF-CLIP + IR (+patch level)	93.3	92.3	88.6	96.4

Table 1: Comparisons with state-of-the-art.

Furthermore, we perform experiments in order to justify the rationale of the proposed objective. More specifically, first we investigate the following question: “What is the reason for obtaining counterfactual defect explanations for the normal images rather than actual explanations of images being normal?” Intuitively, the answer is that the alternative objective is less informative. The experiments in Table 2 validate our choice. That is, instead of the proposed objective, we acquire actual explanations of images being normal from the Anomaly-OV model, and then we force the global normal image embeddings in the downstream model to be more similar to their corresponding LMM-generated text

embedding, abbreviated as AF-CLIP + R (Normal). As demonstrated, this objective slightly improves the baseline performance in only one out of two cases, validating our claim that the proposed objective is more informative. Finally, we investigate the question: “What is the reason for applying the proposed objective only for normal images? That is, what is the reason for not obtaining counterfactual normal explanations for the defective images?” Evidently, defective images can still have normal attributes (e.g., normal shape), thus forcing a defective image with some normal attributes to be less similar to the counterfactual normal explanations could possibly harm the performance. This is experimentally validated through the comparison provided in Table 2, where this alternative objective, abbreviated as AF-CLIP + IR (+ Defective), harms the performance in one out two cases. Note, that this objective is applied for both normal and defective images, that is, it considerably harms the performance of the proposed objective applied only to normal images.

Method	MVTEC		VISA	
	I-AUROC	P-AUROC	I-AUROC	P-AUROC
AF-CLIP	92.3	92.2	87.9	96.1
AF-CLIP + R (Normal)	92.6	92.2	87.6	96.2
AF-CLIP + IR (+ Defective)	92.3	92.1	88.2	96.2
AF-CLIP + IR (Proposed)	93.2	92.2	88.6	96.2

Table 2: Comparisons with alternative objectives.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we proposed a novel method for improving the performance of a downstream CLIP-based model for industrial zero-shot anomaly detection. The proposed method consists of two stages. In the first stage, we use an LMM specialized for anomaly detection, in order to obtain counterfactual defect explanations for the normal images of the auxiliary training dataset. In the second stage, we introduce the knowledge extracted in the first stage to the training process of the downstream model for zero-shot anomaly detection. The additional objective minimizes the cosine similarity between the image embeddings of the normal images and their corresponding embeddings of the LMM-generated counterfactual defect explanations. In this way, we achieve enhanced defect discrimination, employing LMM-produced knowledge and utilizing only the normal images. The experimental evaluation, validates the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Acknowledgment

This work has received funding from the EU’s Horizon CL4 2024 program under Grant Agreement No 101178230 (ENCIRCLE project). This paper reflects only the authors’ view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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